

Empowering professional identity ... through third space collaboration

Claire Toogood and Katy Hale

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845065>

During the 3SS, we shared a pre-publication copy of our paper on “Empowering professional identity and positive outcomes through third space collaboration: A subject lecturer and EAP practitioner case study”. This was subsequently published by the *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* in their special edition on third space in HE in January 2025.

We both are, or have been, third space practitioners in various roles in UK HE institutions and related organisations. As such, we enjoyed the opportunity to share our work with an interested audience and engaged in the discussion and reflection on the Slowposium Forum both on our own paper, and in relation to the work of others. As Katy posted on the Slowposium Forum, in response to one comment we received “... when Claire and I started to collaborate, this was definitely what we were trying to do. We were trying to bridge a gap for students”. We appreciated the opportunity to be part of a community event focusing on exactly that, better experiences and outcomes for students and graduates, through an ambitious, collaborative and rich third space.

Reference

Toogood, C., & Hale, K. (2025). Empowering professional identity and positive outcomes through Third Space collaboration: A subject lecturer and EAP practitioner case study. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education, special issue (33)*.
<https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi33.1196>

About the authors

Claire Toogood

Birmingham Newman University and Harper Adams University

Association of Graduate Careers Advisory Services

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9893-087X>

[LinkedIn](#)

Katy Hale

Aston University

Teaching Fellow – Library and Learning Services